

A geospatial modelling approach to assess flood risk under future scenarios of urban form

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Summary

Simulations of future urban form (road networks, land use type, building density and building type) are needed to provide greater clarity into future urban flooding dynamics. This paper proposes a novel geospatial approach involving advanced geosimulations, artificial intelligence algorithms and hydrodynamic modelling to assess how flood risk is exacerbated under different urban form scenarios. The final output is expected to enhance community-level knowledge and resilience to urban flooding.

KEYWORDS: urban form, flood risk, simulation, hydrodynamic modelling.

1. Introduction

Over the past 30 years, the Greater Mekong Subregion in Southeast Asia (Figure 1) has experienced unprecedented urban land expansion. This has been driven by rural to urban migration as capital cities in the Mekong have better job opportunities, superior quality of life and high foreign direct investment (Li et al., 2018). However, urban land expansion on floodplains, greater impervious surface area and climate change have caused a greater likelihood of fluvial and pluvial flooding within the Mekong which poses a significant hazard to human life and infrastructure (Tierolf et al., 2021).

Figure 1 The Mekong River (white) and its catchment (blue) within Southeast Asia. Figure taken from Conservation International (2021).

Cambodia is one of the most rapidly developing countries within the Mekong Region: its riparian capital city, Phnom Penh, experiences the brunt of this urban growth (Figure 2). Between 2000-2010, Cambodia’s built-up area and population increased by 4.3% and 4.4 % per year, respectively (World Bank, 2015). In 2019, the population of Phnom Penh reached 2.2 million, making it the largest city in Cambodia (National Institute of Statistics, 2019). Additionally, academic literature identified that Phnom Penh had one of the most intense urban expansion patterns within the Mekong between 1990-2015 (Cao et al., 2019). The flood-prone Phnom Penh is unquestionably a pertinent location to research and determine how urban expansion simulations alongside climate projections will impact flood risk.

Figure 2 Phnom Penh urban land expansion between 1990-2020.

The most effective way to understand how urban expansion will impact flooding in Phnom Penh is to utilise sophisticated geospatial techniques to forecast future urban growth scenarios. It is essential to simulate the future layout, character and structure of urban areas to achieve unparalleled outputs on future flooding dynamics. This paper proposes an approach to geospatially model how future urban network layout, land use, density and building type, collectively referred to as urban form, will intensify flooding.

2. Research aim

The goal is to explore and characterise future scenarios of spatiotemporal urban form and assess how these will intensify flooding. To achieve this aim, four objectives have been developed:

- Objective 1: To simulate transportation network, urban land use expansion and building density scenarios through a multi-agent geosimulation.
- Objective 2: To generate building footprints for each scenario modelled using local urban regulation rules and morphological constraints.
- Objective 3: To assess the impact of the simulated urban form on surface water runoff through performing flooding simulations using a hydrodynamic model.
- Objective 4: To develop a web application to view and examine the modelled future urban form and flood outputs.

3. Methodology

The methodology has been split into four stages for each research objective. Figure 3 summarises each stage by presenting the modelling technique used in the coloured rectangles, the software implemented for the modelling in the transparent rectangles and the expected data outputs at each stage in the circles. Each stage will be described in more detail and points of novelty will be highlighted below.

Figure 3 Flowchart of proposed geospatial approach to model urban form evolution and its impact on flooding.

3.1. Multi-agent geosimulation

A multi-agent geosimulation will model the co-evolution of future road network expansion, land use allocation and building density. A transport calculation will be integrated into the road network expansion model to establish which generated roads will be major and minor roads in the simulation (Rui and Ban, 2011). The network expansion model will use techniques such as implementing a competition process and multilayer network approach based on land-use, population, economic and construction factors (Rui et al., 2013; Ding et al., 2021).

The land use allocation model will use the generated network to classify different land use zones, such as residential, commercial, industrial and greenspace areas (Rui et al., 2013). Agents will be created to represent different actors (e.g. government and developer stakeholders) that have important roles in allocating different urban land use functions and types (Xu et al., 2020). The building density of urban areas will be calculated based on land use type, socio-economic factors and attractiveness of the area. Different scenarios of urban land use and road network growth will be considered, such as business as usual and climate change adaptation scenarios.

The co-evolution of urban land use expansion and road networks are an overlooked area of research which requires more investigation to understand the dynamics between these two phenomena. Road network expansion models have rarely been applied to real GIS data and this results in a significant research challenge in implementing these conceptual models to real world data relating to networks and land use (e.g. Ding et al., 2021). This will test the feasibility and performance of these state-of-the-art models when applied to existing data.

3.2. Building generation

The future road network, land use allocation and density values will be used to generate urban blocks and lots (Figure 4). Using the expanded road network, future urban blocks will be defined as an area enclosed by roads. The density values from the land use agent-based model will determine the number of lots that the block is divided into and the sub-division type of the block will be based on the land use type. For example, a residential block subdivision will ensure that all lots have road access, like the subdivision displayed in Figure 4.

Building configurations will then be generated in the lots using a trans-dimensional simulated annealing algorithm (Brasebin et al., 2016, 2018; Zheng and Ren, 2020). The type of building will be generated based on the type of urban block, morphological constraints and local urban planning regulations. Parameters used to simulate the built form will be tuned to ensure simulated building footprints are calibrated accurately to existing buildings in terms of building layout, shape and area.

The building generation model will indicate how different morphological scenarios will impact building location and layout within urban blocks. This will provide invaluable information regarding how building construction influences flood risk. For example, an urban block with several apartments may change flood risk dynamics differently when compared to constructing a row of semi-detached housing.

Figure 4 Diagram representing urban blocks and lots.

3.3. Hydrodynamic model

The generated urban form achieved in stages 1 and 2 of the methodology will be applied to CityCAT to accurately model how the future urban form scenarios will intensify flooding risk. CityCAT is a state-of-the-art hydrodynamic urban flood modelling software developed at Newcastle University (Glenis et al., 2018). Using infrastructure data, such as buildings and road networks, CityCAT can simulate flow pathways, water depths and velocities for rainfall events making it an ideal flood modelling software to use. Climate projections of rainfall will also be modelled when performing the flood simulations.

Performing hydrodynamic simulations under future urban form and climate scenarios will ultimately enable a more comprehensive understanding of flood risk. Going beyond the current state of the art by incorporating changes in urban form in the flood modelling process will produce more detailed and accurate outputs on future flood dynamics. It opens up the potential for advanced flooding analysis, such as topological analytics and neighbourhood vulnerability and exposure to flooding. Understanding how flooding events will affect the topological properties of the simulated and existing road network will provide new insight into the damaged road networks and the impact on traffic capacity during the inundation event (Casali and Heinemann, 2019). Building type and density will indicate how the modelled flood events will impact communities as the number of buildings that will be inundated can be calculated.

3.4. Web application

In the final stage, a web application will be designed to visualise the simulated urban form and flooding outputs. The web application will be in a dashboard format to present key statistics for each scenario produced, such as the number of buildings inundated, flood depths, expected monetary damage and road network accessibility. The application will highlight future risk to the study area and enable decision-makers to make more flood context-related planning choices to mitigate the projected risk.

A web application will be an invaluable communication tool for stakeholders, such as the Mekong River Commission and the Cambodian Ministry of Planning, to explore scenarios and allow non-geospatial users to engage with the research outputs. Stakeholders will be able to identify future flood hotspots, examine flood outputs at an unprecedented spatial scale and explore how different scenarios will impact flooding. This web application will contribute to better urban decision making in Phnom Penh.

4. Expected results

Simulations of urban form would provide numerous benefits over the established approaches to urban expansion flood risk analysis. Urban form simulations at detailed scales will support more localised and context-related planning (Shafizadeh-Moghadam and Helbich, 2015). This will ultimately help shift urban areas to become more resilient, liveable and sustainable. In addition, modelling future urban form will shed light on future flood sources, pathways and receptors in greater detail. These high-resolution urban growth and flooding outputs will inform improved mitigation and protection measures against future flooding.

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